

CHEWA: Evaluating the Impact of an LLM-Enabled Virtual Voice Assistant on Community Health Extension Workers' Decision-Making and Patient Safety

A Multi-Site, Prospective, Pre-Post Comparative Study

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AI	artificial intelligence
AE	adverse event
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
ARFH	Association for Reproductive and Family Health
CHEW	Community Health Extension Worker
CHEWA	Community Health Extension Worker Assistant
CHPRBN	Community Health Practitioners Registration Board of Nigeria
CRERD	Centre for Research, Evaluation Resources and Development
DAC	design, analyze and communicate
FGD	focus group discussion
GP	general practitioner
IRB	Institutional Review Board
LLM	large language model
NG	Nigeria
OAU	Obafemi Awolowo University
PHC	primary healthcare
SMC	Safety Monitoring Committee
SMS	Short Message Service
ToT	training of trainers
UoB	University of Birmingham
UX	user experience
VVC	Viamo Voice Companion

BACKGROUND

Community health extension workers (CHEWs) play a crucial role in Nigeria's health care system, particularly in rural and underserved areas where they often provide the first point of contact for health care services. Their responsibilities include providing preventive care, health education, basic health screenings, and referral of more complex cases requiring higher levels of care. The Nigerian national health policy recognises CHEWs as primary health care providers, acknowledging their role in delivering essential health care in the absence of a sufficient number of physicians (Kress et al. 2016) (O. Abah 2023).

CHEWs undergo structured training in accredited public or private colleges of health technology, schools of nursing, or university teaching hospitals. The Community Health Practitioners Registration Board of Nigeria (CHPRBN) acts as the regulatory board responsible for overseeing their training, licensing, and practice (CHPRBN 2024). In addition, there is a National Standing Order for CHEWs which serves as a guideline outlining their roles, responsibilities, and procedures for delivering health care services (CHPRBN 2024). Despite their broad training and access to reference documentation, CHEWs frequently encounter complex or unfamiliar situations in which immediate access to additional guidance could substantially improve patient care. Studies have highlighted the inequitable distribution of health workers in Nigeria, with physicians and higher-level health-care professionals disproportionately concentrated in urban areas, leading to an increased reliance on CHEWs in rural settings. A report by the World Health Organization found that Nigeria has a doctor-to-population ratio of approximately 0.4 per 1,000 people, well below the recommended 1 per 1,000 ratio (Adebayo and Akinyemi 2022).

Consequently, CHEWs often serve as the primary health care providers in remote areas, despite limited access to decision-support resources. Evidence from Nigeria and other countries suggests that supportive supervision and real-time access to expert advice can enhance the quality of care delivered by CHEWs. For example, a study in South-South Nigeria demonstrated that CHEWs providing primary care under physician supervision via telephone consultation achieved outcomes comparable to those of formally trained medical personnel (Ordinioha and Onyenaporo 2010). The study reported a reduction in adverse events (AEs) following consultations, fewer patients returning with worsening conditions, and lower mortality rates amongst patients managed by CHEWs with telephonic physician support (Ordinioha and Onyenaporo 2010). Additionally, studies on task-shifting models have shown that lower-cadre health workers can provide safe and effective care when given adequate training and structured guidance (Fulton et al. 2011).

Advancements in large language models (LLMs) present a new opportunity to support CHEWs in delivering accurate, timely, and comprehensive health care. By providing real-time, contextually appropriate information, LLMs could help CHEWs overcome existing barriers in accessing medical knowledge (Nazi and Peng 2024).

This study aims to assess the potential of LLMs in frontline health care settings. By addressing gaps in real-time clinical guidance, the integration of LLMs into the CHEW workflow could reduce unnecessary referrals, improve patient outcomes, and strengthen Nigeria's primary health care system.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

In Nigeria, CHEWs are essential to providing frontline health care, particularly in rural and underserved areas where physician shortages are most pronounced. However, they face a significant challenge in their limited access to real-time, comprehensive information that could support timely, accurate decision-making for a wide range of health concerns. Studies have shown that poor utilisation of primary health care facilities in Nigeria is often attributed to perceived poor quality care, with CHEWs sometimes struggling to access the necessary information to manage patients effectively (Luka-Lawal et al. 2020). Existing research indicates that CHEWs can deliver safe and effective care when given adequate support. A study conducted in South-South Nigeria found that CHEWs had good results when given access to physician consultation via telephone (Ordinioha and Onyenaporo 2010). These findings suggest that providing decision-support resources enhances the ability of CHEWs to manage cases at the community level.

Given the demonstrated benefits of telephonic physician support, this study explores whether a system driven by artificial intelligence (AI) (i.e., LLM-based) could serve a similar role in enhancing CHEW decision-making capabilities. Unlike physician-supervised telephone consultations, which require ongoing human resources, an LLM-based system could provide scalable, on-demand access to health care knowledge without relying on direct physician availability. By integrating LLMs into the CHEW workflow, this study seeks to evaluate the feasibility of AI-driven decision support in improving patient outcomes, reducing unnecessary referrals, and strengthening primary health care service delivery in Nigeria.

SPECIFIC STUDY OBJECTIVES

Primary Objective

The primary outcome of this study is the quality assessment of the responses from Viamo's LLM-based clinical decision support system for CHEWs, which is called Community Health Extension Worker Assistant (CHEWA). Responses will be assessed based on a predefined, study-specific evaluation rubric. Each response generated by CHEWA will be systematically assessed by an expert panel against key domains including:

- Adherence to accepted medical science and consensus.
- Relevance to the CHEW's query, ensuring the response directly addresses the specific question asked.
- Clarity of communication in addressing the CHEW's query.
- Contextual appropriateness for a resource-constrained setting, ensuring recommendations consider local norms and are practical given local limitations.

Secondary Objectives

The secondary objectives include:

1. A pre- and post-evaluation of the effect of CHEWA when used by the CHEW to support the management of individual patients, comparing the CHEW's initial management plan (pre-CHEWA) and their final management plan after using the LLM (post-CHEWA), as determined by an expert panel.
2. Evaluation of the user experience and satisfaction of CHEWs using the CHEWA tool to support clinical decision-making.

Materials

The voice-based, toll-free platform developed by Viamo, a Canadian social enterprise, integrates LLMs (such as GPT-4) to deliver verbal responses to health-related queries. This system removes the need for cellular data or internet connectivity, allowing CHEWs to access guidance using basic mobile phones (i.e., a feature phone). In its third iteration, Viamo’s platform enables users to bypass traditional menu-driven navigation and ask open-ended questions directly, broadening access to health care and to educational and agricultural information. Viamo’s platform has demonstrated high engagement, with 24 million users conducting over 814 million searches in 70 languages in the past year, highlighting the demand for AI-driven health information.

Study Design

This is a multisite, prospective, interventional, mixed-methods evaluation of the integration of an LLM into the workflow of CHEWs in Nigeria (Figure 1). The study assesses the quality of LLM-generated responses and its impact on CHEWs’ decision-making, knowledge acquisition, and patient management.

Figure 1. CHEW-CHEWA interaction flow

Study Arms

CHEWs who agree to participate in the study will use the CHEWA tool, a voice-enabled virtual assistant powered by an LLM. Once the CHEW has obtained informed consent from the patient, they may dial into CHEWA at any point before, during, or after the consultation. They can also access the tool after the patient has left, allowing for flexibility when they engage with CHEWA. Importantly, obtaining patient consent does not obligate the CHEW to ask a question - if they feel the consultation does not warrant additional input, they are not required to use the tool. Moreover, the CHEW can also call the assistant to ask questions not specific to a particular patient at any time they want.

The CHEWA tool will guide the CHEW through one of two interaction pathways based on the nature of their query:

Patient-Specific Advice (Arm 1):

- **STEP 1.** The CHEW selects Option 1 (Advice about a specific patient)
- **STEP 2.** The LLM component of CHEWA is then activated, and the CHEW is prompted to (1) describe the relevant health issue of the patient, (2) their planned course of action to address it and (3) ask a direct question to the LLM, getting a real-time response to their clinical query.
Recording/transcript. This step is recorded for the evaluation, as it includes (1) important context for the evaluation panel, (2) the pre-CHEWA management plan proposed by the CHEW, and (3) means to enable the evaluation of the quality of LLM advice (primary objective) and to provide rapid checking of the safety of that advice (safety net).
- **STEP 3.** This step occurs if the CHEW has any further questions they wish to ask. The CHEW can ask as many questions as they like. Training will include guidance on how to interact effectively and efficiently with the LLM and opportunity to practise.
Recording/transcript. This step is recorded to enable the evaluation of the quality of LLM advice (primary objective) and to provide rapid checking of the safety of that advice (safety net).
- **STEP 4.** After completing the interaction, the LLM is deactivated, and the CHEW will be prompted to report whether they followed CHEWA's advice and, if not, what they did differently and why. The CHEW retains full clinical autonomy and may choose to disregard the LLM's recommendations if they deem it to be inappropriate or unnecessary.
Recording/transcript. This step is recorded for the evaluation as it comprises key information about the post-CHEWA management plan.
- **STEP 5.** The CHEW documents their final management plan as part of routine clinical care (written record).
Documentation. This step is critical for the evaluation since it comprises key information about the post-CHEWA management plan.

General Clinical Queries, Not Patient Specific (Arm 2):

- **STEP 1.** The CHEW selects 'Option 2' (advice not about a specific patient).
- **STEP 2.** The CHEW interacts directly with the LLM to seek general clinical or health-related information, and the LLM provides responses accordingly.
Recording/transcript. This step is recorded to enable the evaluation of the quality of LLM advice (primary outcome).

User Experience Questions

At the end of each interaction with the CHEWA tool, CHEWs will be prompted to answer up to two brief user experience questions via a keypad response system before ending the call.

- For patient-specific queries (e.g., diagnosis or management-related):
 - CHEWs will be asked whether they followed the LLM’s advice. If not, they will be asked to provide a reason.
 - They will also be asked whether the information provided was clear and easy to understand.
- For general (non-patient-specific) clinical queries:
 - CHEWs will only be asked whether they found the information clear and easy to understand.

CHEWs are encouraged to complete these questions before disconnecting the call, after which they can proceed with patient care, documentation, or other tasks as usual.

Evaluation Panel

An independent panel of clinical evaluators will assess LLM-generated responses using a predefined rubric covering domains comprising adherence to medical guidelines, relevance to the query, clarity of communication, and contextual appropriateness for a resource-constrained setting (as described in the primary objective). The panel will analyse transcripts from before and after CHEW interactions with the LLM. This comparison will determine whether the CHEW’s management plan changed and will assess whether changes were improvements or deteriorations, therefore quantifying behaviour change.

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA FOR COMMUNITY HEALTH EXTENSION WORKERS

The study will include CHEWs from select communities across two states in Nigeria, Kano and Oyo, recruited by the Association for Reproductive and Family Health (ARFH). Study participants will represent a range of CHEW types, both male and female, currently working in communities across these states, both in public and private health facilities. This selection reflects the diversity of the roles and scope of practice for CHEWs across Nigeria’s community health care landscape, providing a robust sample to evaluate the utility and impact of the CHEWA tool in various contexts of primary care delivery.

Inclusion criteria for CHEWs

Inclusion criteria for CHEWs include:

- CHEWs with minimum competency and complete training, as set out in the National Standing Orders, developed by the CHPRBN; a minimum three months experience in practice as a CHEW; and working in the community and/or health facility in either Kano or Oyo state.
- Ability to competently speak and write in English.
- Willingness and ability to use CHEWA as needed for clinical queries during the study period.
- Willingness to consent for their participation in the study (see Annex A).
- Willingness and ability to commit to study training and procedures.

Table 1. Intended CHEW sample selection by facility type and gender

GENDER	
Male	23
Female	77
FACILITY OWNERSHIP	
Public	91
Private	9

Exclusion criteria for CHEWs

- None

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA FOR PATIENTS

Inclusion Criteria for Patient Participants

Inclusion criteria for participating patients include:

- All patients presenting with a health-related complaint, with consultations provided by participating CHEWs as part of care-as-usual during the study period.
- Willingness to consent for study participation (see Annex B).

Exclusion Criteria for Patient Participants

There is a single exclusion criterion for participating patients:

- Participants who are unable to provide informed consent due to impaired mental capacity or cognitive functioning.

DESCRIPTION OF STUDY INTERVENTION

CHEWA is a voice-first, generative AI intervention that connects basic, non-internet phones with the internet. The intervention uses automatic speech recognition and a pre-trained Generative AI agent to generate spoken responses to open-ended questions.

CHEWA is launched on Viamo's existing platforms, which is a toll-free interactive voice response hotline available to hundreds of thousands of monthly active users in the country. When a caller (e.g., a community health worker) dials into the platform and asks a question, CHEWA transcribes it into text using speech-to-text and analyses the intent using natural language understanding. CHEWA then generates a context-specific response, which is then spoken back to the caller via text-to-speech. The target users of the product are members of offline communities who use basic, non-internet feature phones to get information. It has been used as a job aid or teaching tool to support a range of frontline workers, including CHEWs, agriculture extension agents, and primary school teachers.

STUDY PROCEDURES

CHEW Enrollment and Training

The recruitment and enrolment of CHEWs will be coordinated by ARFH in the selected study areas (Kano, Oyo). CHEWs will be selected to participate in the study until an appropriate sample size is achieved. A proficiency assessment, carried out by ARFH, will be conducted with 120–140 potential candidates; the candidates most proficient in English (50 from each state) will be chosen. These 100 CHEWs will be tested using a set of questions adapted from the British council free-English level test.

Selected CHEWs will be contacted directly, provided with detailed study information, and invited to participate. Informed written consent will be obtained from each participating CHEW (Annex A)—including permission to use their phone number—at the point of training and onboarding by ARFH.

CHEW participants will undergo a structured onboarding process coordinated by ARFH, the Centre for Research, Evaluation Resources and Development (CRERD), and Viamo. CHEWs will initially receive training on how to assess a patient’s capacity to consent. Capacity will be determined based on whether the patient can communicate their choice clearly; understand the risks, benefits, alternatives, and consequences of their decision; and reason and provide logical explanations for their choice. CHEWs will be trained to apply these principles in practice, ensuring that consent is obtained from patients ethically and in line with best practices. It will also include training on the use of the CHEWA tool facilitated by Viamo with support from ARFH, with specific guidance on using the LLM-enabled support tool to address patient queries. Viamo will organize a training of trainers for the team, before cascading to the CHEWs selected for the study. Additionally, participating CHEWs will complete an onboarding survey via the Viamo platform, to capture baseline information on their previous digital tool usage, expectations, and confidence in using the tool. A support line will be accessible throughout the study, allowing CHEWs to ask questions and receive assistance with study procedures as needed.

Patient Enrollment

During the study, CHEW participants will conduct consultations as per usual care. Before each consultation, the CHEW will provide a brief explanation of the study to eligible patients and invite them to participate. Written informed consent will be obtained from all patients (Annex B). A written consent form has been developed. If the patient can read and write, the form will be handed over to the patient to read and then sign if consent is given. If the patient cannot read and write in English, the consent will be translated to the patient in Yoruba (Oyo) or Hausa (Kano), a thumbprint will then be taken of the patient if consent is given. All signed consent forms will be collated and stored according to protocol.

Safety Net Review

A group of general practitioners (GPs) with at least five years of experience will conduct the safety net review that supports the CHEWs. CRERD will oversee, recruit, and train the GPs for the safety net review process. The safety net aims to ensure that if the CHEWA tool was to give information or advice that was deemed unsafe, this would be identified, and correct information would be provided to the CHEW as quickly as possible to reduce any risk of harm to the patient. GPs serving in the safety net role will be given the CHEW-CHEWA transcripts by Viamo in near real time. Each transcript will be reviewed by a single GP within one hour of the patient being seen by the CHEW, thus conducting a single safety net review. If the GP safety net reviewer identifies any concerns, specifically instances where the LLM may have provided the CHEW with unsafe advice, the GP will promptly contact the CHEW directly. The CHEW will then either confirm that they did not act on the bad advice or acknowledge that they did. If the unsafe advice was acted upon, the CHEW and GP safety net reviewer will discuss appropriate next steps, including whether in-person follow-up is needed and within what time frame. Once a plan is finalised, the CHEW will contact the patient to inform them of any necessary changes in their care. The CHEWs will be expected to have retained appropriate patient contact details for this purpose. If the patient does not have contact information, there are two possible options:

1. The patient will be asked to provide the contact of a close relative who can reach them. The CHEW will call the close relative whilst the patient is still at the facility to confirm the contact and explain the reason why the patient has provided this contact information.

- Alternatively, if the patient cannot provide a relative's contact, his/her descriptive house address will be obtained, and a home visit can be carried out if the need arises.

Expert-Level Evaluation

CRERD will oversee the evaluation panel whose members will provide independent evaluation of the primary and secondary outcomes. CRERD will recruit and train a separate group of GPs, each with at least five years of experience and based in Kano or Oyo states. They will review the outcomes as described in this protocol, with Kano state GPs reviewing interactions by CHEWs in Kano and similarly GPs from Oyo reviewing the interactions carried out by CHEWs from Oyo. Each panel will consist of two GPs for first-pass evaluation and a third GP, usually one who is more senior, to act as a tiebreaker, when required. The two first-pass panel members will conduct blinded evaluations independently and have a discussion to reach consensus if needed; where consensus is not achieved, the third panel member will conduct a tie-breaking evaluation.

To ensure consistent and accurate evaluations, all panel members will participate in a one-day training as part of their onboarding, covering the study protocol and instructions on the evaluation rubric, including reviewing a set of 10 example cases together.

OUTCOMES

Primary Outcome

The primary outcome of this study is the quality assessment of CHEWA responses based on a predefined, study-specific evaluation rubric. An expert panel of experienced clinicians will assess the CHEWA responses by reviewing interaction transcripts, including the questions posed by CHEWs and the corresponding answers generated by the LLM-based virtual assistant.

Two expert panel members will independently evaluate each response based on four key domains. Responses in Arm 1 (patient-specific advice) will be evaluated across all four domains: (A) adherence to accepted medical science and consensus, (B) relevance to the CHEW's query, (C) clarity of communication, and (D) contextual appropriateness for a resource-constrained setting. In contrast, responses in Arm 2 (general, non-patient-specific clinical queries) will be assessed only on domains A, B, and C, as contextual relevance and suitability are less applicable to broader clinical inquiries.

For each question, where the two evaluation panel members are more than 1 point apart on the 4-point Likert scale, they will discuss the case. If, following discussion, their rating remains more than 1 point apart, evaluation will pass to a senior panel member who will provide the final definitive score.

Evaluation guidelines for the four key domains are listed below.

Adherence to accepted medical science and consensus. Does the response from CHEWA align with established medical guidelines and evidence-based practice?

Responses will be rated on a 4-point Likert scale:

- 1. Nonadherent**—The response contradicts established medical guidelines or poses a clear safety risk.
- 2. Partially adherent**—Some elements align with guidelines, but key recommendations are incorrect or incomplete.
- 3. Mostly adherent**—The response is broadly aligned with medical consensus but has minor gaps or inaccuracies.
- 4. Fully adherent**—The response is fully aligned with medical guidelines and best practices.

Relevance to the CHEW's query. Does the response directly address the CHEW's specific question?

Responses will be rated on a 4-point Likert scale:

1. **Irrelevant**—The response does not answer the question or is entirely off-topic.
2. **Minimally relevant**—The response partially addresses the query but lacks key information and/or contains distracting unnecessary information.
3. **Mostly relevant**—The response is mostly appropriate but includes some unnecessary information and/or omits some key information.
4. **Highly relevant**—The response directly answers the query with clear, pertinent information.

Clarity of communication. Does the response effectively convey necessary information in a clear, structured, and professional manner, appropriate for the intended audience?

Responses will be rated on a 4-point Likert scale:

1. **Unclear**—The response is confusing and poorly structured, making it difficult to understand.
2. **Partially clear**—The response conveys some necessary information but lacks coherence or is not well-structured.
3. **Mostly clear**—The response is generally well-structured and understandable but could be improved in certain areas.
4. **Fully clear**—The response is professional, well-structured, and easy to understand, effectively conveying all necessary information without unnecessary complexity.

Contextual appropriateness for a resource-constrained setting. Does the response align with locally applicable clinical guidelines and provide feasible recommendations given the CHEW's working environment?

Responses will be rated on a 4-point Likert scale:

1. **Not contextually appropriate**—The response contradicts local guidelines (if available) or recommends entirely inaccessible resources/interventions.
2. **Minimally contextually appropriate**—Some elements align with local guidelines (if available) and feasibility, but key recommendations are impractical or misaligned.
3. **Mostly contextually appropriate**—The response largely aligns with local guidelines (if available) and is generally feasible, though minor discrepancies or impractical suggestions exist.
4. **Fully contextually appropriate**—The response adheres to local guidelines (if available) and provides practical, locally feasible recommendations, fully considering resource limitations.

Secondary Outcomes

PRE- AND POST-CHEWA ANALYSIS OF RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PATIENT-SPECIFIC QUERIES

This secondary outcome will assess whether the CHEW's management plan changes after interacting with the LLM and whether these changes improve or worsen patient care. To establish a baseline, the CHEW will be asked: 'Can you summarise the patient's background, your planned next steps, and what is your first question'? After completing their interaction with the LLM component of CHEWA, the CHEW will then be asked: 'Did you follow CHEWA's advice?' and the CHEW will have to provide a response. If they did not follow or only followed some of the advice, the CHEW will be prompted to answer: 'What did you do differently to CHEWA's advice, and why'? The evaluation panel will be given all relevant documented information in order to determine the ground truth for each case and to compare both the pre-CHEWA and post-CHEWA management plans against this reference.

The same two-member expert panel will assess the transcripts, recommendations, and safety net review data. They will be asked to answer two questions:

1. Did the CHEW's management plan change after using CHEWA? (Options=Yes/No)
2. If yes, was the change better, equally appropriate, or worse compared with the CHEW's original management plan, and explain why. (Options=Better/Equally Appropriate/Worse, with white box space to provide their reasoning)

If the two evaluators disagree or are uncertain, they will discuss the case to reach a consensus. If consensus is not achieved, a third senior clinician will evaluate the case and serve as the tiebreaker.

The analysis will determine how often interaction with CHEWA affected the behaviour of the CHEW and whether it affected behaviour positively or negatively (reported as percentages).

It should be noted that the post-CHEWA plan represents the CHEW's stated intention at that moment in time. It is possible that, following this step, additional discussions with the patient that introduce new information not available to the LLM may result in a final documented management plan that differs from the immediate post-CHEWA plan. Whilst we will characterise the frequency of these discrepancies, cases where the final documented plan differs from the immediate post-CHEWA plan will be excluded from the pre- versus post-CHEWA comparative analysis to ensure that we are assessing only the direct impact of the LLM interaction.

All interactions will be fully transcribed into text. Audio recordings will also be available and may be used at the discretion of the expert evaluators if they believe listening to the recording would supplement their decision-making; however, their use is not mandatory.

USER EXPERIENCE ASSESSMENT

This secondary outcome aims to evaluate the user experience of CHEWs working with the CHEWA tool to support clinical decision-making. Understanding the CHEWs' experiences will help identify factors influencing engagement, satisfaction, and confidence, as well as potential challenges and areas for improvement in tool functionality and usability.

Immediate Post-Interaction Feedback

At the end of each interaction, CHEWs will be prompted via the tool to respond to a maximum of two questions regarding their experience using the tool. Responses will be provided through keypad entry, which will later be used for analysis.

For patient-specific queries (e.g., diagnosis or management-related) the questions are:

1. Did you follow CHEWA's advice?
 - Press 1 for 'I followed all recommendations'
 - Press 2 for 'I followed some recommendations'
 - Press 3 for 'I followed none of the recommendations'
 - If options 2 or 3 were selected, the CHEW will then be asked an open-ended question, 'What did you do differently to CHEWA's advice, and why?' for which the CHEW will be encouraged to answer in as much detail as possible.
2. Was the information provided by CHEWA clear and easy to understand?
 - Press 1 for Yes
 - Press 2 for No

For general (non-patient-specific) clinical queries, CHEWs will only be asked whether they found the information clear and easy to understand.

End-of-Study Focus Group Discussions

At the conclusion of the study, a small focus group discussion will be conducted with 20 participating CHEWs per state to gain deeper insights into their experiences using CHEWA over the study period. The discussion will be guided by open-ended questions including but not limited to:

1. Did the CHEWA tool integrate smoothly into your workflow, or did it cause any disruptions?
2. Has using CHEWA increased your confidence in managing patient cases?
3. At what point during the consultation did you decide to use CHEWA?
4. If the CHEWA tool was always available to you, how would you like to use it in the future (e.g., as a general knowledge tool or to assist you with specific patients)?
5. Did patients express any concerns or hesitations about the use of CHEWA in their care?
6. Would you benefit from additional training or guidance on how to use CHEWA effectively in consultations?

These insights will help inform future iterations of CHEWA, ensuring that it is both clinically useful and practical for frontline health care workers in resource-limited settings.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS PLAN

Sample Size Considerations

We aim to recruit 100 CHEWs (50 each from two states). It is expected that by the end of the study the CHEWs will have undertaken at least 2500 interactions with the CHEWA tool. In terms of ensuring patient safety, this volume of reviews can be appropriately supported by the safety net reviewers in each state, assessing responses within an hour of the interaction.

It has been suggested that the sample size required for the assessment of a Likert scale outcome should be based on a combination of factors: the number of items assessed, the confidence level, the tolerable error, the expected coefficient of variation at the population level, and the pairwise correlation coefficient between items (Park, J.W. and Jung, M.S. 2009).

For our outcome, we have four items under consideration: (A) adherence to accepted medical science and consensus, (B) relevance to the CHEW's query, (C) clarity of communication, and (D) contextual appropriateness for a resource-constrained setting. We expect these items to be weakly positively correlated, as they measure different aspects of response quality. As we have no prior information on which to base more precise estimates, we consider pairwise correlation coefficients (ρ) of 0.3 and 0.5.

Park and Jung suggest that for 4-point scales for each item (as in our case), the coefficient of variation is likely to be lower than 1, due to rater avoidance of extreme response categories. If this were the case, for example, considering a coefficient of variation (C) of 0.5 with $\rho=0.5$, the feasible sample size of 1000 would result in an error of less than 3%, with the necessary sample size for a 3% tolerable error under these conditions being 667 interactions.

With a more conservative suggested coefficient of variation (C) of 1, implying a mean combined Likert score equal to the standard deviation, calculations suggest that a proposed sample size of 1000 interactions would be sufficient to achieve an expected error of between 4% and 5%, for both assumed values of ρ . A 5% tolerable error would be achieved at 730 interactions for $\rho=0.3$, and at 960 interactions for $\rho=0.5$.

Thus, the feasible sample size of 1,000 interactions would allow us to achieve a tolerable error of 5% for conservative estimates of the coefficient of variation up to 1, and for pairwise correlation coefficients up to 0.5.

We plan to recruit for 2,500 interactions, which exceeds the minimum required for the primary outcome. This larger sample ensures we have sufficient cases to conduct a robust pre-post analysis within Arm 1, where we aim to analyse 1000 interactions. If fewer than 1000 interactions are available, we will include all interactions from Arm 1; if more are available, we will analyse the last 1,000 to minimise the impact of early learning curve effects. Despite the sample size calculations, all 2500 interactions will be evaluated by the expert panel for the primary outcome assessment, providing a comprehensive understanding of response quality across the study.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics will be used to summarise the baseline characteristics of participating CHEWS and key study measures. Additionally, the study will include a qualitative characterisation of the types of questions CHEWs ask across primary health care domains. This analysis will provide insights into their specific information needs, guiding future improvements to CHEWA and identifying areas for additional training and support. By categorizing queries related to triage, diagnosis, treatment planning, referral decisions, health education, and logistical concerns, we can better tailor CHEWA to the roles filled by CHEWs within the community. Further, analysing the distribution of questions, such as those concerning infectious diseases versus chronic conditions, may highlight gaps in existing resources and training. These themes will serve as an initial framework, with the study data informing potential refinements.

Primary Outcomes

Quantitative data will be analysed using appropriate software tools.

Secondary Outcomes

Qualitative data, including user experience feedback, will be analysed thematically using qualitative analysis software. This analysis will provide insights into how CHEWs interact with the tool, their perceived usability, and any barriers or facilitators to its integration into their workflow.

DATA TYPES AND SOURCES

Table 2 below highlights the various data points collected for the study.

All data except for qualitative focus group discussions are housed on the Viamo secure password protected platform. Qualitative focus group data will be recorded electronically and uploaded on CRERD's encrypted password protected cloud server, along with their quality assured transcripts. We shall implement strict data access control. Only key research staff including CRERD data analysts will be given login details to datasets.

Table 2. CHEWA data collection by type and source.

DATA TYPE	SOURCE	DETAILS
Raw interaction recording	Viamo	Interaction recording between CHEW-CHEWA
English-translated transcripts	Viamo	CHEW-CHEWA interaction transcripts
LLM-generated content	Viamo	CHEWA generated advice, within the interaction transcript
Safety net data	CRERD	Safety issues noticed by clinical officer/PHC physician
CHEW UX priority questions	Viamo	CHEW answers to UX priority questions during each interaction
CHEW UX focus group discussion	CRERD	CHEW answers to UX focus group discussion questions
Clinician panel evaluation results	Viamo	Clinician evaluation panel results

Abbreviations: CHEW, community health extension worker; CHEWA, Community Health Extension Worker Assistant; LLM, large language model; CRERD, Centre for Research, Evaluation Resources and Development; PHC, primary health care; UX, user experience.

DATA MONITORING PLAN

Study data will be monitored by the local partner for completeness, timeliness, accuracy, and compliance with protocols. Data audits will be conducted at intervals throughout the study to allow feedback from CHEW participants and implementation of necessary modifications if needed.

To ensure data quality, participating CHEWs will complete an onboarding survey via the Viamo platform, capturing baseline information on their previous experience with digital tools, expectations, and confidence in using the tool. Additionally, CHEWs will receive structured training during onboarding to ensure high quality data entry and appropriate use of the tool. The quality and completeness of study data will be actively monitored by the local partner for timeliness, accuracy, and adherence to study protocols.

Regarding qualitative data integrity, transcription and translation errors by the LLM are expected to be minimal. However, to mitigate potential errors, a sample of transcripts will be manually reviewed to assess accuracy. If systematic errors are identified, adjustments will be made to the transcription process, and additional training may be provided to CHEWs on clear speech input and verification of responses.

Safety and Risk Monitoring

This study is interventional. To ensure the safety of study participants and minimise potential associated risks with the study procedures, we have anticipated the following potential risks:

Table 3. Identified potential risk and mitigations

RISK	MITIGATION
Unauthorised access or exposure of sensitive health information could occur during data collection, transfer, or storage.	Implement robust encryption for data at rest and in transit (AES 256-bit or similar), control access via secure credentials, and regularly audit access logs. Anonymize patient and CHEW data where possible and ensure strict data handling protocols.
Some patients may feel uneasy or distrustful if they perceive that the CHEW is relying on a digital tool rather than direct expertise, potentially impacting their satisfaction with the consultation.	Train CHEWs on how to introduce the CHEWA tool to patients, emphasising that it enhances their ability to provide accurate information and quality care. Ensure that CHEWs obtain consent and are prepared to handle patient questions about the tool and can reassure patients about its purpose.
Using CHEWA during consultations may create a barrier between CHEWs and patients, potentially impacting rapport or patient comfort.	Emphasise to CHEWs the importance of obtaining consent and once obtained, maintaining patient engagement, explaining that CHEWA is a supportive tool to help ensure thorough care.
Safety net review not happening on time.	Implement automated reminders or time-sensitive reminders on the Viamo data sheet to ensure timely safety net reviews. Assign a dedicated team member to monitor adherence to timelines and follow up with any delays.
Inability for safety net reviewer to contact the CHEW for follow-up (where needed).	Ensure alternative communication channels are available (e.g., via in-person visit) and confirm contact details regularly.
CHEW unable to reach patient for follow-up (where needed).	Provide the CHEW with multiple methods to contact the patient (e.g., SMS, in-person visit) and inform them of backup strategies during training if the first attempt fails.

Abbreviations: AES, Advanced Encryption Standard; CHEW, community health extension worker; CHEWA, Community Health Extension Worker Assistant; SMS, short message service.

Viamo is fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation. To ensure confidentiality, informed consent will be obtained from all participants (CHEWs and patients) providing clear information about the study and their right to privacy. The data in Viamo’s database is secured and encrypted with restricted access. All members of the research team understand the importance of confidentiality and the imperative to use the data received only for the purpose of this research.

All data to be shared publicly will be de-identified with no direct link to participants. On the dashboard, results will not include CHEW or patient names or phone numbers. All data stored on Viamo’s database will be kept for at least five years or may be deleted from the platform upon request from PATH. The data can also be downloaded and shared with PATH for further use or storage if necessary.

Safety Monitoring Committee

A safety monitoring committee (SMC) will be established by CRERD to oversee participant safety and ensure the ethical conduct of the clinical trial. The SMC will be composed of independent experts, including clinicians, data scientists, bioethicists, and patient representatives, who are not directly involved in the study's day-to-day operations.

The committee's primary responsibilities will include the regular review of safety data, adverse event reports, and protocol adherence. They will convene monthly or as needed to assess safety concerns, review interim data, and make recommendations regarding trial continuation, modification, or termination based on safety considerations. In addition, the SMC will conduct an early safety check (within one to two weeks of study initiation) to evaluate whether the safety net is working as intended and whether any adjustments are necessary. The SMC's findings and recommendations will be documented and communicated to the study sponsor and partnering organisations, investigators, funders, and relevant health authorities, including the Nigeria Primary Health Care Development Agency and the Ministry of Health.

Adverse Event Reporting

AEs are defined as any untoward medical occurrence during the study, which may or may not be related to the use of the Viamo platform, for example:

- **Patient safety concerns**—Any events where the advice or actions based on the LLM response may have caused harm, delay in treatment, or worsened patient conditions.
- **Delayed or incorrect referrals**—Instances in which the LLM's guidance led to a delay or error in referring the patient to higher levels of care when needed.
- **Inaccurate diagnosis or treatment advice**—Instances in which the LLM's response may have contributed to an incorrect diagnosis or inappropriate treatment, potentially compromising patient safety.
- **Failure to escalate care**—Situations where the CHEW did not escalate care appropriately due to unclear or incomplete advice from the LLM, potentially leading to patient harm.

AEs will be carefully monitored, documented, and managed by the study team using a standardized AE reporting form. All adverse events will be reported to the principal investigator upon detection, irrespective of severity or perceived causality, within 24 hours.

Severity assessment and grading will be graded based on severity:

- **Mild**—Minimal discomfort with no interference in daily activities.
- **Moderate**—Some interference in daily activities requiring minimal intervention.
- **Severe**—Significant impairment of daily activities necessitating medical intervention.
- **Life-threatening**—Immediate risk of death related to adverse event

Documentation of each AE report will include:

- Description of the event.
- Date and time of onset.
- Duration and resolution.
- Actions taken in response to the adverse event.

Serious AEs will be reported to the sponsor (i.e., PATH) as soon as possible but no later than 10 days after any party involved in the study becomes aware of the event. This allows PATH as the sponsor to inform the relevant regulatory bodies within the 15-day limit set out by the US Food and Drug Administration. The regulatory bodies include but are not limited to the ethics committee or institutional review board (IRB) and the relevant national regulators (Nigeria and USA).

ROLE OF KEY INVESTIGATORS

Table 4 shows study responsibilities and assigned roles for each investigator.

Table 4. CHEWA study roles, tasks, and responsibilities, by investigator and organisation

	Study design and development	Community/public engagement	Training	Data management	Clinical care	Data and sample collection	Data analysis	Report writing
Dr Elizabeth Omoluabi CRERD	●		●	●	●	●	●	●
Mr Charles Ohikhuai Viamo	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Ms Noha Ghaly Viamo	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Ms Lydia Odeh Viamo	●	●	●	●		●	●	●
Dr Xiaoxuan Liu UoB	●						●	●
Dr Vaishnavi Menon UoB	●						●	●
Prof Alastair Denniston UoB	●						●	●
Dr Lucinda Archer UoB	●						●	●
Mira Emmanuel-Fabula PATH	●						●	●
Bilal Mateen PATH	●						●	●
Prof Akanni Akinyemi Obafemi Awolowo University	●		●	●		●	●	●
Dr Kehinde Osinowo ARFH	●	●	●		●	●		●
Mr Samson Olorunju ARFH	●	●	●	●		●	●	●

Abbreviations: ARFH, Association for Reproductive and Family Health; CRERD, Centre for Research, Evaluation Resources and Development; OAU, Obafemi Awolowo University; UoB, University of Birmingham.

STUDY TIMELINES

Table 5 presents the study activities by month

Table 5. CHEWA study timeline

	2024			2025						
	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG
Protocol development workshop										
Protocol review										
Advocacy to state of implementation										
DAC and Gates Foundation review protocol										
Protocol update and finalisation										
Approved protocol from PATH										
Submission of protocol to Oyo and Kano States Ethical Committee in Nigeria										
Generate CHEW and expert evaluators contact list										
Training of expert evaluators										
Virtual TOT for Viamo NG, ARFH, and CRERD teams										
Nigeria IRB approvals obtained										
Onboarding and training of CHEWS										
LLM tool development										
Internal testing of LLM tool										
Deployment of LLM tool to CHEWs										
Monitor results sheet and daily quality checks										
FGD with CHEWs										
Analyse results from tool										
Cleaned study dataset										
Safety monitoring reports										
Preliminary data analysis report										
Pre-print scientific article										
Final project report										

Abbreviations: ARFH, Association for Reproductive and Family Health; CHEW, community health extension worker; CRERD, Centre for Research, Evaluation Resources and Development; DAC, Design, Analyze and Communicate; FGD, focus group discussion; IRB, institutional review board; LLM, large language model; NG, Nigeria; ToT, training of trainers; UoB, University of Birmingham.

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Consent form for participating in the study for evaluating the impact of an IIm-enabled virtual voice assistant on community health extension workers' decision-making and patient safety: a multi-site, prospective, pre-post comparative study

Consent form for community health extension workers (CHEWs)

1. We are asking you to be in a research study.

This is a study about a Community Health Extension Worker Assistant (CHEWA) tool that helps health care workers to improve their capacity to provide high-quality healthcare to their patients by asking questions via a mobile phone. We are asking you to be in the study because you are a health care worker providing services to patients in the health facility or community in the state where this tool is to be tested. We plan to collect interactions between you and the patients who come to you for consultation. The main goal of this study is to evaluate the quality of CHEWA's responses using a specific evaluation guide created for the study.

Researchers from PATH, Viamo, Centre for Research, Evaluation Resources and Development (CRERD), and Association for Reproductive and Family Health (ARFH) are doing this study.

Here are important points about this study:

- You do not have to be in the study. You can say “yes” or “no” or leave after joining. If you say “no” or drop out after entering the study, we will treat you the same.
- If you join, you will be in the study for about 20 days.
- The researchers may remove you from the study if you are not able to follow the directions of the study staff or if the study ends early.
- The study involves dialing a number on your mobile phone, asking and answering questions about the patients, recording your consultation, and home visits or phone calls to patients.
- All research studies have risks. You are most likely to receive responses that may not make sense or accurate. You may also get resistance from some patients who may feel uneasy or distrustful if they see that you are relying on a digital tool rather than using direct knowledge to attend to them. Prior to utilizing the tool, it is essential to obtain consent from patients. Additionally, any responses that seem inaccurate must be validated by a senior medical officer.
- This study may help you to improve delivering accurate, timely, and comprehensive healthcare services to your patients by providing real-time information appropriate for the case you are handling. It will also serve as a training opportunity while contributing to improving the tool.
- What we learn from this study may help other people in the future with how consultation with patients can be done using an artificial intelligence tool.
- There are no costs to you to be in the study. But if you decide to participate, you will receive a transportation and communication stipend based on the number of days and interactions you generate.
- We will keep your study information confidential. We will use a code in place of your name and only members of the research team will have access to your details.
- We will share the overall results of the study with you. We may call you or send you an email informing you about the results.
- We may write an article or share the study results at meetings or on websites, but your personal details will not be mentioned.

2. How will you find out if you can be in the study?

Before you decide if you want to join the study, we will need to see if you meet the study requirements. You will need to agree to participate and sign this form before we see if you are able to be in the study. We will ask for your phone numbers, address, and permission to record your voice.

3. What will happen during the study?

Here is what will happen in this study:

Consent from patient: You will first obtain informed consent from the patient if you want to use the tool for a patient. You may as well dial the CHEWA number at any point before, during, or after the consultation. You can also access the tool after the patient has left.

Patient-specific advice: You will dial the CHEWA number and do the following:

- Describe the health issue of the patient.
- Record how you plan to treat the patient.
- Ask the CHEWA tool questions on how to treat the patient.
- Report your final management action for the patients.
- Take a final survey on what you will do with the information you received from CHEWA.

Focus Group Discussion: We will ask you to join a group of other people to discuss your thoughts, experiences and how you feel about the tool at the end of the study. You do not have to talk about anything that makes you uncomfortable.

4. Your rights

You have rights in this study:

- You do not have to be in this study. You can say yes or no to joining. You can leave the study at any time. If you do not join or leave early, you will not have any penalties. You should not feel pressure to join or stay in the study.
- By signing this consent form, you do not lose any rights you normally have.
- If we learn new information about the study, we will tell you. You can decide if you want to stay in the study after you learn this new information.

5. Who to contact if you have questions?

If you have questions about this study, or you believe you have been hurt as a result of the study, or have questions about your rights in this study, please call the Principal Investigator.

Name: Elizabeth Omoluabi, PhD

Address: No. 20, F Road, Citec Mboru Mount Pleasant, Off Jabi Airport Road, Abuja, Nigeria

E-mail: elizomoluabi@gmail.com

Telephone number: +234 808 020 1587.

Confirmation of written consent

Use of your information for future research

Do you agree to take part in this study? (initials or thumbprint in the box)

Yes

No

Study participant

Signing your name below means you voluntarily choose to be in this research study. It also means you have asked any questions you want to ask. You will get a copy of this form to keep.

Printed name

Date

Signature of participant

**Thumbprint
of participant**

Member of research team

Signing my name below means I have explained this research study to you and answered your questions to the best of my ability. I will give you a copy of this form to keep.

**Signature of person
obtaining consent**

Date

Consent form for patients

1. We are asking you to be in a research study

This is a study about a Community Health Extension Worker Assistant (CHEWA) tool that helps health care workers to improve their capacity to provide high-quality healthcare to their patients by asking questions via a mobile phone. We are asking you to be in the study because you attend this health facility for your health services, and we want the CHEW to use this tool while discussing your health issues. We plan to collect interactions between you and the CHEW. The main goal of this study is to evaluate the quality of CHEWA's responses using a specific evaluation guide created for the study. Researchers from PATH, Viamo, Centre for Research, Evaluation Resources and Development (CRERD), and Association for Reproductive and Family Health (ARFH) are doing this study.

2. Here are important points about this study

- You do not have to be in the study. You can say “yes” or “no” or leave after joining. If you say “no” or drop out after entering the study, we will treat you the same.
- If you join, you will be in the study for about 20 days.
- The study involves the CHEW dialing a number on a mobile phone, asking and answering questions about your condition, recording the consultation, and home visits or phone calls to you if follow up is needed.
- All research studies have risks. If you join the study, you are most likely to feel unsafe giving your personal details or experience anxiety seeing the CHEW using a tool attend to you. You do not need to bother as we will keep all your information confidential. The CHEW will also ensure responses from the tool are validated by a senior medical officer.
- This study may help the CHEW to provide you with personalized and better and more accurate care.
- There are no costs to you to be in the study.
- We will keep your study information confidential. We will use a code in place of your name and only members of the research team will have access to your details.
- We may write an article or share the study results at meetings or on websites, but your personal details will not be mentioned.

3. Your rights

- You do not have to be in this study. You can say yes or no to joining. You can leave the study at any time. If you do not join or leave early, you will not have any penalties. You should not feel pressure to join or stay in the study.
- By signing this consent form, you do not lose any rights you normally have.

4. Who to contact if you have questions

If you have questions about this study, or you believe you have been hurt because of the study, or have questions about your rights in this study, please call the Principal Investigator, listed below.

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E-mail: elizomoluabi@gmail.com

Telephone number: +234 808 020 1587.

Confirmation of written consent

Use of your information for future research

Do you agree to take part in this study? (initials or thumbprint in the box)

Yes

No

Study participant

Signing your name below means you voluntarily choose to be in this research study. It also means you have asked any questions you want to ask. You will get a copy of this form to keep.

Printed name

Date

Signature of participant

Thumbprint
of participant

Member of research team

Signing my name below means I have explained this research study to you and answered your questions to the best of my ability. I will give you a copy of this form to keep.

Signature of person
obtaining consent

Date

Witness

Signing below means that the study participant whose thumbprint is above chose to be in this research study. It also means I was present the whole time the study was being explained. I confirm that the participant had a chance to ask questions. The participant will get a copy of this form to keep.

Printed name

Date

Signature of witness